

ARSENIC, CHROMIUM, FLUORIDE CONTAMINATION OF GROUND WATER IN INDIA AND REMEDIATION BY LOW COST ADSORBENTS;

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INTRODUCTION

Large scale industrial growth in India has caused serious concern regarding the susceptibility of ground water contamination due to heavy metals . Waste materials near the factories which is subjected to reaction to percolating rain water and reaches the ground water level . This percolating water picks up a large number of heavy metals and reaches the aquifer system and degrades the ground water quality The most important factor which distinguishes metals from other pollutants is that they are not biodegradable once they enter the environment .These metals Al(III), Cr(VI),Fe(III), Ni(II), Mn(II),Mg(II),have cumulative effects at low levels when present in drinking water and ground water .The adsorbtion of these metals in the body system is high and excretion is slow . Studies on the relationship between the carcinogenicity of a metal and its ability to decrease the fidelity of RNA synthesis with DNA polymerase.The genetic toxicity of metals have shown levels of some metals [in blood serum , plasma nucleic acid and tissues] increase with tumour initiation and development .

ARSENIC

The traditional reputation of arsenic as a poison is largely due to the higher toxicity of the As(III) ion, whereas elemental arsenic (As[V]) and organic arsenic compounds are commonly considered less toxic. The normal amount of arsenic in hair is 0.08-0.25 mg/kg, whereas 1 mg/kg is an indication of toxicity. The normal amount of arsenic in nails is 0.043-1.08 mg/kg. The normal amount of arsenic in urine is 0.005-0.40 mg/kg (1.5 D). The maximum permissible limit of arsenic in drinking water is 0.05 mg/L. Widespread arsenic contamination has been found in different regions of West Bengal due to dissolution of arsenic-containing bedrock. The high arsenic content of the drinking water has become a major public health issue in six districts of West Bengal in India, where an estimated 30 million people dependent on tubewell water sources have been adversely affected. The districts are in the eastern sector of West Bengal, extending 450 km from north to south bordering Bangladesh. The severely affected districts are Malda, Mursshidabad, Nadia, Bardhaman, 24 Parganas (North), and 24 Parganas (South). The arsenic content in the groundwater ranges from 0.01 to 0.59 mg/L in as many as 830 villages in this area. Tubewells have been dug to a depth of 120 to 50 feet. Table 1a shows the arsenic levels in drinking water in West Bengal, and Table 1b shows a study of arsenic level in the tissue and body fluid of the people of West Bengal (Chakraborty et al., 1999).

INDUSTRIES RELEASING ARSENIC

Arsenic is used in the metallurgical industry, glassware and ceramic industries, dye and pesticide manufacturing industries, and petroleum refineries. Chemicals containing arsenic are used in the manufacture of herbicides and pesticides. In West Bengal, a factory manufacturing acetocopper arsenite, a pesticide, polluted drinking water in the southern part of Calcutta. Arsenic is released into the surface water through mining and burning of coal as well as copper smelting. Rivers flowing through the coal fields of Bihar have been reported to carry large amounts of arsenic, responsible for downstream arsenic poisoning in West Bengal. According to studies, the arsenic contamination of the Damodar in West Bengal is mainly due to dumping wastes from the coal mines along the river bed (Susheela, 1999).

HEALTH HAZARDS DUE TO HIGH ARSENIC INTAKE

As(III) ion causes arsenicosis in human beings. Symptoms of arsenic poisoning are abdominal pains, vomiting, diarrhea, and pain in the extremities, followed later by numbness and tingling of the extremities, palmoplantar hyperkeratosis, Mees lines on the fingernails, and deterioration in motor and sensory responses. Symptoms of chronic arsenicalism include dermal lesions, peripheral neuropathy, skin cancer, and peripheral vascular disease. Bony fish and freshwater mussels contain a high content of arsenic. As, Hg, Pb, Cd are highly toxic even at low concentrations. Zn(II) in some metallo-enzymes is substituted by Cd(II). Arsenic acts on the biological system in the following ways: Toxic As(III) inhibits enzyme activity by reacting with ligands containing sulphhydryl (-SH) groups. As(III) attacks -SH groups of an enzyme (i.e., inactivation of pyruvic dehydrogenase by complexation with As[III]), preventing the generation of ATP in the citric acid cycle. Pyruvic dehydrogenase is highly sensitive to arsenic because of its interaction with two -SH groups of lipoic acid, leading to pyruvate accumulation. As(III) ion readily crosses the placental barrier and causes fetal damage. Arsenic when absorbed in the biological system can undergo bio-transformation under in vivo conditions, as the As(V) ion, or arsenate, can be reduced to the As(III) form, or arsenite. The half-life of this bio-transformed arsenite is three to five days, when it can cause harm to the system (Susheela, 1999).

Arsenicosis is a chronic disease with a significant latency period for non-cancer and cancer effects. There appears to be discrepancy in the literature regarding latency, with some reports of 2 years being the minimum for hyperpigmentation and keratosis. Researchers in Bangladesh suggest that 5 years is the minimum latency, whilst some other estimates suggest that this is 9 years. Latency for cancers is also unknown, but it is estimated to be of the order of 20 years. The proportion of a population exposed to elevated arsenic that will develop arsenicosis is uncertain, but may be significant. Medical treatments for arsenicosis are not fully developed. There is an indication that switching to arsenic-safe water and anti-oxidants may reverse symptoms in early stages. The proportion of a population exposed to elevated arsenic from drinking water that will go on to develop arsenicosis is unknown.

The World Health organization (WHO) has modeled the progression of arsenicosis

using data from Samta, Bangladesh. The range of those affected over 30 years was 15.75% in the lowest estimate scenario to 29.25% in the highest estimate scenario. Variation in the estimates of mortality from cancers was between 5.0 and 6.5%. This implies a significant overall health burden for those affected. It is not clear whether early removal of arsenic-contaminated water would reduce the onset of cancers, but it is assumed that it would have some impact because of the cumulative nature of the risk.

More recent work suggests that anti-oxidants within vitamins A, C, and E and possibly compounds containing zinc and selenium also work to reverse symptoms. A recent controlled trial was performed in Bangladesh, but this remains to be published and may require further controlled clinical trials. However, this does indicate the necessity of combining both environmental and medical interventions for arsenicosis (Howard, 2003).

8 districts /830 villages in 58 blocks	Conc of As in water mg\l		
Total samples of analysed	<0.01	>0.05	> 0.01
34900	56.5	43.5	38.7

Total samples of analysed	% of samples above normal level
HAIR	
3530	74.0
NAIL	
3620	74.0
SKIN	
163	[1.2-29.3]
URINE	
7240	83.6

TABLE 2 ADSORBENTS FOR REMOVAL OF As [III] , As[V] FROM WATER

ADSORBENT	REFERENCE
Ferric Sulphide bed	Lee et al 1972
Bauxite sample	Balient Ambro 1974
Chitin mixture	Elson CM et al 1980
Amorphous iron oxide	Pierce et al 1982
Manganese Dioxide soil	D.W Huang 1983
Lake sediments	Takamastu 1985
Coal fly Ash	Sen AK and Arnab K.De 1987
Coral limestone	Shigeru 1992
Activated carbon impregnated with metallic Ag,Cu	Rajakovic 1992
Ganga sand	Vaishaya RC 1993
Synthetic Birnessite	Scott 1995
Basic Yttrium carbonate	Warsy SA 1996
Iron coated spent catalyst	Liu JC ;Huang 1997
Chemically treated sawdust	Nag A 1998
Manganese Dioxide coated sand	Sanjeev Bajpai 1999
Lanthanum impregnated Sawdust carbon	Raji .C; Anirudhan1999
Ferric oxide impregnated carbon	Brian Reed 2000

FLOURIDE

There are two types of fluorosis ,dental and skeletal fluorosis Dental fluorosis occurs when the level of fluoride in water exceeds 1.5 mg/l. Teeth due to their high calcium content easily take up fluoride. Prolonged intake of water having fluoride levels exceeding 3 mg/l leads to skeletal fluorosis leads to bow legs and knock knees which affects children as well as adults symptoms of this disease tingling knees. sensation in the legs followed by pain, stiffness of the back.

FLOURIDE RELEASING INDUSTRIES

Large scale of industrial growth has caused serious concern regarding the suscepility of ground water due to heavy metals . Waste materials near the factories are subjected to reaction with percolating rain water and reaches the groundwater level . The permissible limit for fluoride in drinking water 1.5mg/l [.Industries using hydrofluoric acid or fluoride salts in their technology i.e.aluminium industries,steel and enamel, pottery and glass industries,oil refineries , pharmaceuticals and cosmetic industries which liberate flourous gases to the atmosphere and are the main cause of industrial induced Fluorosis.Certain beverages like dry tea leaves contain 39.8 –68.6 ppm fluoride Chewing items like supari ,tobacco,pan contain 3.8-38.0 ppm fluoride . Use of fluoride bearing toothpaste and mouth wash lead to Fluorosis .[Table 3]

SYMPTOMS OF SKELETAL FLUOROSIS

In patients showing effects of skeletal fluorosis, the medical reports suggest accumulation of fluoride ion more in cancellous bones than in cortical bone, because of porosity, copious blood supply, presence of trabecular bone surfaces and bone engulfing bone marrow. The fluorosed bone shows characteristic structural changes viz. *increased bone mass and density. *exostosis (bone outgrowth) at bone surfaces *increased osteoid seam and resorption surfaces. *increased trabecular bone volume, cortical porosity and periosteocytic lacunar surface.

*formation of unmineralized cartilaginous loci within the trabeculae of the cancellous bone

*maximum ill effects are detected in the neck spine, knee, pelvic and shoulder joints and small joints of hands and feet *severity of skeletal fluorosis, increases pain which is associated with rigidity and restricted movement of cervical and lumbar spine, knee, pelvic and shoulder joints.

*further severity results in stiff spine i.e. Bamboo spine, immobile knee, pelvic and shoulder joints. *crippling deformity further results: Kyphosis, Scoliosis, Hexion deformity, Paraplegia, Quadriplegia and Osteophytes

MECHANISM OF FLUORIDE ACCUMULATION IN THE SOIL

Fluoride in lithosphere and soil found chemically in compound forms i.e. fluorapatite, fluorite and other rock forming minerals in order of 0.06% - 0.09% of the earth crust. Salt deposits of marine origin also contribute fluoride to the soil. The fluoride accumulation in soil is governed by (i) natural solubility of fluoride compounds (ii) acidity of the soil (iii) presence of other minerals & chemical compounds (iv) amount of water present. The fluoride accumulation in soil is also depth factor.

ACCUMULATION OF FLUORIDE IN THE HUMAN BODY

The accumulation of fluoride in the human body is due to the high reactivity of fluoride ion with calcium of teeth bones, resulting to form calcium fluorophosphate (fluorapatite) crystals and leaving unbound calcium in certain locations in the same tissue, which gets calcified and in turn results in stiffness of tissues & joints causing skeletal fluorosis in late stages. The chemical substitution of fluoride ions replacing hydroxyl ions and calcium hydroxy-apatite in bones is due to strong affinity between fluoride and biological apatite of the body. Once the apatite/fluorohydroxyapatite forms, it remains chemically stable until the tissue is reabsorbed or metabolized. A little of fluoride increase in the body by diffusion and absorption. Nearly 90% of fluoride in the body is associated with calcified tissues. The fluoride effects on proteins and on DNA molecules are also possible.

There are two types of fluorosis, dental and skeletal fluorosis. Dental fluorosis occurs when the level of fluoride in water exceeds 1.5 mg/l. Teeth due to their high calcium content easily take up fluoride. Prolonged intake of water having fluoride levels exceeding 3 mg/l leads to skeletal fluorosis, which leads to bow legs and knock knees which affects children as well as adults. Symptoms of this disease include tingling knees, sensation in the legs followed by pain, stiffness of the back.

TABLE : SUMMARISED INFORMATION ON THE OCCURENCE OF FLUORIDE IN GROUNDWATER IN VARIOUS STATES OF INDIA		
STATE	DISTRICT	FLUORIDE mg/litres
Andhra Pradesh	Ananthapur	0.8-3.5
	Nalgonda,Prakasam	
	Visakhapatnam	0.50-7.5
Bihar	Hyderabad	0.3-1.9
	Palamu	2.24-7.54
	Jamui	2.96-8.16
	Gadhwa	1.60-4.8
	Bhabhna	1.80-3.0
	Rohtas	2.50-3.0
	West Champaran	1.60-2.0
	Gopalganj	1.60-2.5
Gujarat	Mehsana	1.58-9.9
Haryana	Gurgaon	0.17-24.5
Jammu&Kashmir	Doda	0.05-4.21
	Ghat ,Monkhil,	
	Malwas ,Bhagwa	
	Khastigarh ,Bharat,	
	Chamalwas, Batroo	
Karnataka	Dharwad	0.40-18.0
	Gulbarga	0.20-5.60
	Raichur	0.40-8.5
Maharastra	Jalgoan	0.11-3.0
	Bhandara	1.50-10.2
	Nagpur	0-4.4
M.P.	Shivpuri&Jabua	1.50 -4.2
Punjab	Sangrur	0.28-4.0
Tamil Nadu	Madurai	0-0.27
	Dindigul	0.2-1.03
	Tuticorin of Chidambarar	above 0.5
U.P	Unnao	0.12-19.0
	Agra	0.28-22.0
	Allahabad	1.00-1.50
	Dehradun	0.02-0.10

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REMOVAL METHODS

The author wishes to draw attention toward the fact that various technologies are available for removing Cr (VI), including reduction and precipitation, ion-exchange, precipitation of chromate with barium or lead, ion-flotation, electro dialysis, liquid-liquid extraction and reverse osmosis, the process of adsorption has an edge over other methods, due to its simplicity and sludge free clean operation. The most widely used method is to first detoxify Cr (VI) by reducing to the Cr (III) form, which is about 100 times less toxic. This can be accomplished with reducing agents such as SO_2 , ferrous-sulphate, sodium bisulphite or other sulphite. Then precipitation of chromium is induced by the addition of a base. A major problem with this type of treatment is the disposal of precipitated chromium hydroxide. Metal hydroxides tend to be highly hydrated and voluminous stable colloids containing as much as 80% water by volume due to the slower replacement of coordinate water for hydroxide ions

. Ion-exchange treatment does not present a sludge disposal problem and has the advantage of reclamation of Cr (VI). However, Ion-exchange treatment does have disadvantages of being expensive, being poorly selective for chromate over foreign anions and of having a critical flow rate necessary for efficient removal

Biological removal of toxic Cr was tried using an *Enterobacter cloaca* strain that reduces under anaerobic conditions. [Komori 1990] The bacteria *Enterobacter cloaca* removes toxic Cr VI by reducing it to Cr III, this trivalent Cr forms $\text{Cr}(\text{OH})_3$ which can be separated using negatively charged materials. This method may also create sludge problems.

Activated carbons are widely used as adsorbents for purification of aqueous solutions of chromium [Jung .I.Kim 1997] as adsorption has an edge over other methods, due to its simplicity and sludge free clean operation. Activated carbons are used in full scale operations in developed countries, however their use is not suitable for developing countries due to their high manufacturing cost. Most water treatment technologies suitable for the developed countries are expensive for towns and small industries of the developing countries because of limitation of funds and lack of skilled man power. There is an increasing search for low cost adsorbent material made from locally available

waste material and plant substrata Some low cost adsorbents selective for Cr(VI) have been tested in the laboratory by batch and column technique pH, concentration and flow rate on break-through capacity have been investigated

The author compared some adsorbents which are available through out the year Human Hair was a poor adsorbent at pH range 1-5 removed 1.1mg Cr/ gm Similarly Brick kiln ash showed only 50% removal as compared to Fly ash at pH 1.3 from chromeplating wastewater as shown in Figure 2 Bituminous coal at pH 2 removed 2.5mg/gm Adsorbent made from a mixture Fly ash – Chinaclay showed 100% removal at pH 2 from solution 4.3mg Cr (VI)/L .Columns packed with Sawdust a natural inexpensive material, available everywhere can be utilized as low cost adsorbent for the removal of CrVI from aqueous solution, the adsorption capacity was determined as 97.5 mg/5gm or 19.5mg/gm at pH~2 Break through capacity as a function of pH is plotted in Figure 3. Rice straw a inexpensive material can be utilized as low cost adsorbent for the removal of CrVI from aqueous solution [Figure 4], the adsorption capacity was determined 25mg Cr /gm Baggase is reported to remove 80.80% at pH 6-7 from solution 3.5gm Cr (VI)/L Tea leaves carbon [TLC] can play an important role in treatment processes of metal bearing industrial effluents, a cheap carbonaceous adsorbent made from waste tea leaves Break through capacity 39.3mg/gm. In Figure 5, Cr(VI) removal as as function of pH and carbon dosage can be seen. The amount of TLC required for 100% Cr(VI) removal 433mgCr (VI)/L carbon dosage 1200mg/L at pH 1.5 –2.0 Author compares TLC to Groundnut husk carbon GHC It can be seen that, Activated Groundnut husk carbon at pH range 0.5-1.7 showed 100% removal from 10mg Cr (VI)/L solution, carbon dosage 2400mg /L in Figure 6 Presence of holocellulose and lignin on sawdust and rice straw can be explained for removal of CrVI from aqueous solution.

Sigworth and Smith have proposed the possibility of heavy metal precipitation on the carbon surface by nucleation as one of the pathways for heavy metal removal by activated carbon. The adsorption of Cr (III) on red mud is highly dependent on pH=5 -6 Cr(III)adsorption on red mud also depends the upon contact time, sorbent dose and initial concentration of Cr(III) Figure7 Red mud showed 99.6%Cr (III) removal from a solution containing 150 mg Cr (III)/ 100 ml .Iron hexamine modified sawdust removed 19.53 mg Cr VI /gm in presence of other ions in pH range 2-6 Figure 8 Alternative low cost method is removal of Cr(VI) from tannery effluent

using waterweeds , water weeds *Salvinia molesta* and *Spirodela polyrhiza* were allowed to grow in the tannery effluents from Tanneries .

This research has been limited to a study of adsorption capacities at different pH for some low cost adsorbents *Aloe vera* and *Water hyacinth root* for fluoride . There is a need to describe the mechanisms responsible for removal of metal ions Cr , Ni ,Pb and anion F⁻ from aqueous solution by low cost adsorbents .) It has been observed that, there is a pressing need for development and introduction of simple and inexpensive methods of water treatment.(iv) To deal with the problem an awareness should be created among villagers about the ill effects of drinking contaminated water. There should be transfer of water treatment techniques to the villages. There is a need for water quality surveillance. If villagers are trained to use water testing kits to monitor the purity of water independently, they will realise the gravity of the problem.The water pollution menace can be overcome by community participation.

Rice straw , Bagasse and Sawdust are natural inexpensive materials ,which are easily available and do not require chemical pretreatment .Exhibit exceptionally high degree of Cr(VI) adsorption , thus can be utilized for treatment of industrial waste effluents containing Cr(VI)

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